

Intraoperative Fluid Administration in ENT Surgery: Impact on Acid-Base Balance and Renal Function (Experience from a Developing Country)

K. Damaan¹, S. Skakri¹, A. Abidi¹, S. Benhamza¹, M. Lazraq¹, Y. Miloudi¹, A. Bensaid¹

¹Department of Anesthesiology and Critical Care, 20 August 1953 Hospital, Hassan II

ABSTRACT

Background: Excessive administration of 0.9% sodium chloride may induce hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis and impair postoperative organ function. This study aimed to evaluate the incidence of perioperative hyperchloremic acidosis in major ENT surgery and to assess its association with intravenous fluid volume and early postoperative renal function.

Methods: This was a prospective observational study approved by the institutional ethics committee (Approval No. 2025/RSI/127; ethics committee registration number: 2024/BOC/187). The study was conducted in the ENT operating theatre between November 2024 and March 2025. Adult patients (>18 years) undergoing procedures lasting more than 3 hours were included. Patients with pre-existing renal failure, preoperative acidosis, or surgeries requiring controlled hypotension were excluded. Pre- and postoperative biological parameters were correlated with fluid volume, type of surgery, operative duration, and perioperative complications using Fisher's exact test.

Results: Forty patients were included (male-to-female ratio = 2.64). Oncologic procedures represented 92.5% of cases. The mean intraoperative fluid volume was 2.91 L, and all patients received 0.9% sodium chloride exclusively. The incidence of hyperchloremic acidosis was 22.5%. A highly significant association was found between fluid volume >4 L and hyperchloremic acidosis ($p = 0.00002$). Operative duration was also significantly associated with acidosis occurrence. Although 10% of patients developed KDIGO stage 1 acute kidney injury on postoperative day 1, hyperchloremic acidosis was not statistically associated with acute kidney injury ($p = 0.213$).

Conclusion: Hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis is a frequent iatrogenic complication in major ENT surgery, strongly associated with high intravenous fluid volumes and prolonged operative duration. These findings support an individualized perioperative fluid strategy favoring balanced crystalloid solutions. Larger multicenter studies are needed to confirm these findings.

KEYWORDS: Hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis; Normal saline (0.9% NaCl); Perioperative fluid therapy; Major ; ENT surgery; Renal function; Intraoperative fluid resuscitation.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
02 June 2026

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

1. INTRODUCTION

Perioperative fluid management is a key component of anesthetic practice, ensuring hemodynamic stability and adequate tissue perfusion [1]. However, the type and volume of administered fluids may influence acid-base balance, particularly during prolonged surgical procedures [2,3].

The administration of intravenous fluids can induce metabolic disturbances, including acidosis, depending on their composition and physicochemical properties [4]. In

particular, chloride-rich solutions such as 0.9% sodium chloride have been associated with the development of hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis [5,6].

This disturbance, often underrecognized, may have important metabolic consequences and may affect renal function in the postoperative period. In this context, the objective of this study was to evaluate the risk of hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis associated with perioperative fluid administration in

Intraoperative Fluid Administration in ENT Surgery: Impact on Acid-Base Balance and Renal Function (Experience from a Developing Country)

major ENT surgery, as well as its impact on renal function during the first 48 postoperative hours.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a prospective, observational, descriptive, and analytical study approved by the institutional ethics committee (Approval No. 2025/RSI/127; ethics committee registration number: 2024/BOC/187). conducted in the ENT operating room of 20 August 1953 Hospital, Casablanca, from November 2024 to March 2025.

Inclusion criteria included patients aged over 18 years who underwent surgical procedures lasting more than 3 hours. Exclusion criteria were patients with pre-existing renal failure and/or metabolic acidosis, as well as procedures requiring controlled hypotension (middle ear and endonasal surgery).

All data were collected using a standardized data collection form including patient identification, epidemiological parameters (age, sex), medical history, surgical history, ASA physical status classification (I-IV), laboratory tests (serum chloride, bicarbonate, creatinine, and blood urea), intraoperative fluid volume, hemodynamic

parameters (heart rate, urine output, systolic, diastolic, and mean arterial pressure recorded at predefined time points), type of surgery, duration of the procedure, and intraoperative and postoperative complications.

Hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis was defined according to biochemical criteria described in the literature, including increased serum chloride levels and decreased bicarbonate concentration [7,8]. The ASA physical status classification followed standard clinical practice.

Statistical analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel (Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, WA, USA). The association between fluid volume and hyperchloremic acidosis was tested using Fisher's exact test, with a significance threshold set at $p < 0.05$

3. RESULTS

3.1. Demographic Characteristics

The study included 40 patients. The majority were between 50 and 70 years of age, with a mean age of 61.6 years. There was a male predominance, with a male-to-female ratio of 2.64 (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Distribution of age according to sex.

3.2. Medical and Surgical History

The majority of patients had no significant medical history:(72.5%; n = 29) or surgical history (82.5%; n = 33) (Tables 1 and 2).

Table 1: Distribution of Patients According to Medical History

Medical History	Number of Patients	Percentage
Hypertension	7	17.5%
Type 2 Diabetes	1	2.5%
Atrial Fibrillation	1	2.5%
Ischemic Heart Disease	1	2.5%

Intraoperative Fluid Administration in ENT Surgery: Impact on Acid-Base Balance and Renal Function (Experience from a Developing Country)

Hypertension Hyperthyroidism	+	1	2.5%
No Medical History		29	72.5%

Table 2: Distribution of Patients According to Surgical History

Surgical History	Number of Patients	Percentage
Prior cholecystectomy	2	5.0%
Prior surgery for carcinoma of the tongue and maxilla	1	2.5%
Prior surgery for a facial mass	1	2.5%
Prior surgery for an abdominal mass	1	2.5%
Prior surgery for carcinoma of the cheek	1	2.5%
Prior surgery for ameloblastoma	1	2.5%
No prior surgical history	33	82.5%

3.3. ASA Physical Status Classification

The majority of patients were classified as ASA II 75% (n = 30), while 25% (n = 10) were classified as ASA III. No patient was classified as ASA I, IV, or V (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Distribution of patients according to ASA physical status classification.

Intraoperative Fluid Administration in ENT Surgery: Impact on Acid-Base Balance and Renal Function (Experience from a Developing Country)

3.4. Distribution of Patients by Type of Surgery

The series was predominantly composed of oncologic procedures (n=37;92.5%). Other interventions (stomatologic

and ENT procedures) accounted for a minority of cases (n=3;7.5%), without a significant impact on the overall trend (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Distribution of patients by type of surgery.

3.5. Distribution of Patients According to Operative Duration

In this series, the mean operative duration was 6.95 hours (approximately 6 hours and 57 minutes): In this series, the mean operative duration was 6.95 hours (approximately 6 hours and 57 minutes): 52.5% of procedures lasted between

3 and 6 hours, 32.5% lasted between 7 and 10 hours, 15% lasted more than 10 hours

These prolonged durations may have a direct impact on metabolic homeostasis, tissue perfusion, and the occurrence of complications, particularly hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Distribution of patients according to operative duration.

3.6. Hemodynamic Monitoring During Fluid Administration

Intraoperative fluid administration was guided by standard clinical parameters, including heart rate, blood pressure, and urine output. The majority of patients (n= 37; 92.5%) were

monitored using a combination of heart rate, blood pressure, and urine output, whereas in (n=3) 7.5% of patients, monitoring was limited to heart rate and blood pressure (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Distribution of patients according to the type of intraoperative hemodynamic monitoring.

3.6.1. Arterial Blood Pressure

Continuous arterial blood pressure monitoring was performed in all patients (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Mean arterial blood pressure values at the different time points of the procedure.

3.7. Type of Fluid Administered

In this series, all patients (100%) received 0.9% sodium chloride as the sole intraoperative intravenous fluid.

3.8. Volume of Fluid Administered

The mean intraoperative fluid volume was 2.91 liters. 60% (n= 24) of patients received between 2 and 4 liters, while 25% (n=10) received more than 4 liters. In contrast, 15% (n=6) of patients received volumes ≤ 2 liters (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Distribution of patients according to the volume of intraoperative fluid administered.

3.9. Intraoperative Complications

30 % of patients (n = 12) experienced at least one episode of intraoperative hypotension, whereas 70% (n = 28) had no hemodynamic complications during the procedure. Among hypotensive patients, management primarily involved a

combination of fluid administration and vasopressor therapy: 50% (n = 6) received fluids combined with norepinephrine, 33.3% (n = 4) were treated with fluids alone, and 16.7% (n = 2) received fluids combined with ephedrine (Figures 8 and 9).

Figure 8: Distribution of patients with or without intraoperative complications.

Figure 9: Management of intraoperative hypotension.

3.10. Preoperative and Postoperative Laboratory Values

Analysis of laboratory parameters showed an increase in serum chloride levels in the postoperative period (106.52 vs. 102.28 mmol/L), accompanied by a decrease in serum

bicarbonate (19.88 vs. 22.15 mmol/L). Additionally, a moderate increase in serum creatinine and blood urea levels was observed postoperatively (Table 3, Figure 10).

Table 3: Preoperative and Postoperative Laboratory Parameters

Laboratory Parameter	Mean ± SD
Preoperative serum chloride	102.28 ± 3.21
Postoperative serum chloride	106.52 ± 4.04
Preoperative serum creatinine	7.77 ± 2.12
Postoperative serum creatinine	9.39 ± 3.08
Preoperative serum bicarbonate	22.15 ± 1.56
Postoperative serum bicarbonate	19.88 ± 4.07
Preoperative blood urea	0.32 ± 0.15
Postoperative blood urea	0.37 ± 0.12

Figure 10: Postoperative variation in laboratory parameters compared with preoperative values.

Intraoperative Fluid Administration in ENT Surgery: Impact on Acid-Base Balance and Renal Function (Experience from a Developing Country)

These laboratory changes are consistent with the development of hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis, which was observed in 22.5% of patients (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Distribution of patients according to the occurrence of hyperchloremic acidosis.

3.11. Postoperative Adverse Effects

Postoperative adverse effects were limited in this series. Functional renal impairment (acute kidney injury, KDIGO

stage 1) was observed in 4 patients (10%). No neurological, gastrointestinal, or hemostatic complications were recorded (Table 4).

Table 4: Observed Postoperative Adverse Effects

Postoperative Adverse Effect	Number of Patients	Percentage
Cerebral function impairment	0	0%
Renal function impairment	4	10%
Gastrointestinal complications	0	0%
Hemostatic or bleeding complications	0	0%

3.12. Cross-Analysis

3.12.1. Operative Duration and Hyperchloremic Acidosis

Cross-analysis between operative duration and the occurrence of hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis showed a clear positive correlation. Among patients with operative durations exceeding 10 hours, all patients (100%, n = 6) developed hyperchloremic acidosis. In contrast, among

procedures lasting 7 to 10 hours, the incidence was markedly lower, with only one case among 13 patients. Among patients with operative durations of 3 to 6 hours, only 2 out of 21 patients developed this complication.

Fisher's exact test confirmed a highly significant association between operative duration and the occurrence of hyperchloremic acidosis ($p = 2.18 \times 10^{-5}$). (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Distribution of patients according to operative duration and the presence of hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis.

3.12.2. Fluid Volume and Hyperchloremic Acidosis

The analysis revealed a clear dose-response relationship between the volume of intraoperative intravenous fluid and the occurrence of hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis. Among patients who received more than 4 liters, all (100%, n = 6) developed hyperchloremic acidosis. In contrast, among patients who received between 2 and 4 liters, acidosis was

observed in only 2 patients compared with 18 who did not develop this complication. Among patients who received 2 liters or less, only one case of acidosis was reported. Fisher's exact test confirmed a highly significant association between fluid volume greater than 4 liters and the occurrence of hyperchloremic acidosis (p = 0.00002). (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Distribution of patients according to the volume of fluid administered and the presence of hyperchloremic acidosis.

Intraoperative Fluid Administration in ENT Surgery: Impact on Acid-Base Balance and Renal Function (Experience from a Developing Country)

3.12.3. Type of Surgery and Hyperchloremic Acidosis

In this series, all observed cases of hyperchloremic acidosis (100%, n = 9) occurred in the context of oncologic surgery, whereas no cases were reported following non-oncologic ENT or stomatologic procedures (Figure 14).

Fisher's exact test demonstrated a statistically significant association between the oncologic nature of the procedure and the occurrence of hyperchloremic acidosis ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 14: Distribution of patients according to the type of surgery and the presence of hyperchloremic acidosis.

3.12.4. Medical and Surgical History and Hyperchloremic Acidosis

In this series, all patients who developed hyperchloremic acidosis (n = 9) had no notable medical comorbidities, and the vast majority (8 out of 9 cases) had no prior surgical history. Only one case of acidosis was observed in a patient with a history of prior oncologic cheek surgery.

No cases of hyperchloremic acidosis were reported among patients with comorbidities such as hypertension, type 2 diabetes mellitus, chronic atrial fibrillation, or ischemic heart

disease, nor among those who had previously undergone cholecystectomy or maxillofacial surgery.

3.12.5. Postoperative Adverse Effects and Hyperchloremic Acidosis

Among the patients who developed postoperative renal impairment (n = 4), two also presented with hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis. No cases of cerebral, gastrointestinal, or hemostatic impairment were observed among patients with hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis. (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Association between hyperchloremic acidosis and renal function impairment.

3.12.6. ASA Score and Acidosis

Analysis of the relationship between ASA physical status score and the occurrence of hyperchloremic acidosis did not demonstrate a statistically significant association in this series. Patients classified as ASA II accounted for the majority of hyperchloremic acidosis cases, which primarily reflects their numerical predominance in the study population. Conversely, no cases of acidosis were observed among ASA III patients, despite a theoretically more vulnerable clinical profile.

These findings suggest that, in this population, the occurrence of hyperchloremic acidosis was more closely related to perioperative factors — such as prolonged operative duration,

intravenous fluid volumes, and the exclusive use of chloride-rich solutions — than to baseline clinical status as assessed by the ASA score. Therefore, the ASA score does not appear to be an independent predictive factor for hyperchloremic acidosis in this cohort, which appears to be predominantly iatrogenic and related to perioperative management conditions.

3.12.7. Perioperative Hypotension and Acidosis

Among the 12 patients who experienced perioperative hypotension, 3 (25%) developed hyperchloremic acidosis, compared with 6 (21.4%) of the 28 patients who did not experience hypotension. This difference was not statistically significant (Fisher's exact test, $p > 0.05$), (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Distribution of patients according to perioperative hypotension and the presence of hyperchloremic acidosis.

4. DISCUSSION

The hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis observed in our study is consistent with a well-established pathophysiological framework based on Stewart's physicochemical approach. According to this model, pH is determined by three independent variables: the partial pressure of CO₂, the total concentration of weak acids, and the strong ion difference (SID) [1]. The administration of chloride-rich solutions such as 0.9% NaCl, characterized by a SID of zero, leads to an increase in plasma chloride concentration and a reduction in SID, resulting in metabolic acidosis. This interpretation is supported by the work of Siggaard-Andersen and Fogh-Andersen, who emphasized that base excess is merely a descriptive parameter, whereas SID allows identification of the underlying mechanisms of acid-base disturbances [2].

The central role of strong ions in acid-base regulation has been confirmed by several experimental studies. Alfaro et al. demonstrated that pH variations during hemorrhage are primarily driven by changes in SID [3]. Historically, metabolic acidosis observed after fluid administration was attributed to "dilutional acidosis"; however, this concept has

been increasingly challenged. Prough and White showed that this phenomenon is more closely related to chloride load than to simple bicarbonate dilution [4]. These findings were further supported by Waters et al., who demonstrated that the ionic composition of infused fluids plays a key role in acid-base alterations [5]. Similarly, Miller and Waters highlighted the predominant role of chloride in the development of metabolic acidosis [6].

From a clinical perspective, multiple studies have clearly established the relationship between 0.9% NaCl administration and the occurrence of hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis. Scheingraber et al. demonstrated that rapid saline infusion induces a dose-dependent metabolic acidosis [7]. Likewise, Waters et al. reported that during prolonged surgical procedures, the observed acidosis is predominantly hyperchloremic and independent of tissue hypoperfusion [5]. Prough and Bidani further confirmed that hyperchloremic acidosis is a predictable consequence of saline infusion [8]. Our findings are consistent with these data, showing a significant association between high fluid volumes (>4 L) and the occurrence of hyperchloremic metabolic

Intraoperative Fluid Administration in ENT Surgery: Impact on Acid-Base Balance and Renal Function (Experience from a Developing Country)

acidosis ($p = 0.00002$).

The impact of fluid composition has also been widely investigated. Rehm et al. demonstrated that chloriderich solutions, whether crystalloids or colloids, induce metabolic acidosis through a reduction in SID [9]. Similarly, Waters et al. showed that acid-base changes following volume expansion depend primarily on the type of fluid administered [10]. In contrast, the use of balanced solutions helps preserve acid-base equilibrium. Gan et al., in a randomized clinical trial, demonstrated that physiologically balanced plasma expanders better maintain acid-base homeostasis during major surgery [11]. These findings are consistent with current guidelines, which recommend the preferential use of balanced solutions in both perioperative and critical care settings.

Beyond metabolic effects, hyperchloremia may have deleterious consequences on renal function. Wilcox demonstrated that increased plasma chloride induces afferent arteriolar vasoconstriction, leading to reduced renal blood flow and glomerular filtration rate [12]. In our study, although no statistically significant association was found between hyperchloremic acidosis and acute kidney injury-likely due to the limited sample size-the underlying physiological mechanism supports a potential causal relationship. Furthermore, metabolic acidosis has been associated with systemic complications, including pulmonary outcomes, as reported by Eberhard et al. [13].

Our results also suggest that the main determinants of hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis are related to perioperative factors rather than patient baseline characteristics. Prolonged operative duration and large volumes of administered fluids appear to be key contributors, consistent with previous findings [5]. The association with carcinologic surgery is likely indirect, reflecting longer operative times and greater fluid requirements.

Finally, fluid therapy should be considered a therapeutic intervention in its own right. Several studies have reported the occurrence of hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis following the administration of 0.9% saline, related to its high chloride content and its impact on acid-base balance [14,15]. Guidelines from ANDEM, SRLF, and SFAR emphasize the importance of an individualized, goal-directed fluid strategy guided by hemodynamic monitoring to optimize tissue perfusion while minimizing complications [16]. Our findings support this approach and suggest that limiting chloride load and favoring balanced solutions may reduce the risk of hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis, particularly in prolonged surgical procedures.

Limitations:

This study has several limitations. First, the relatively small sample size may limit the generalizability of the findings. Second, the single-center design may introduce selection bias and reduce external validity. Third, the observational nature of the study does not allow for establishing a causal

relationship between fluid administration and hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis. Finally, certain potential confounding factors, such as intraoperative hemodynamic variations and individual patient characteristics, may not have been fully controlled.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis represents a notable perioperative complication in major ENT surgery, closely associated with prolonged operative duration and high volumes of intravenous fluid administration using 0.9% sodium chloride. Its clinical impact appears to be predominantly renal and more closely related to perioperative management conditions than to baseline patient characteristics.

From a practical standpoint, these findings support the use of titrated and monitored fluid therapy, limitation of chloride-rich fluid administration, and preferential use of balanced crystalloid solutions whenever possible, particularly during prolonged or complex surgical procedures.

These exploratory findings should, however, be confirmed by larger multicenter comparative studies in order to better define the impact of fluid management strategies on perioperative metabolic disturbances.

REFERENCES

- I. Stewart PA. : Modern quantitative acid-base chemistry. *Can J Physiol Pharmacol.* 1983, 61:1444-1461.10.1139/y83-207
- II. Siggaard-Andersen O, Fogh-Andersen N: Base excess or buffer base (strong ion difference) as measures of a non-respiratory acid-base disturbance. *Acta Anaesthesiol Scand Suppl.* 1995, 107:123-128. 10.1111/j.1399-6576.1995.tb04346.x
- III. Alfaro V, Pesquero J, Palacios L: Acid-base disturbance during hemorrhage in rats: significant role of strong inorganic ions. *J Appl Physiol.* 1999, 86:1617-1625. 10.1152/jappl.1999.86.5.1617
- IV. Prough DS, White RT: Acidosis associated with perioperative saline administration: dilution or delusion? . *Anesthesiology.* 2000, 93:1174-1175. 10.1097/00000542-200011000-00005
- V. Waters JH, Miller LR, Clack S, Kim JV: Mechanism of hyperchloremic nonanion gap acidosis *Anesthesiology.* 1997, 87:1009-1010. 10.1097/00000542-199710000-00050
- VI. Miller LR, Waters LH, Provost C. : Mechanism of hyperchloremic acidosis . *Anesthesiology .* 1996, 84:482-483.. 10.1097/00000542-199602000-00044
- VII. Scheingraber S, Rehm M, Sehmisch C, Finsterer U : Rapid saline infusion produces hyperchloremic acidosis in patients undergoing gynecologic surgery. *Anesthesiology.* 1999, 90:1265-1270. 10.1097/00000542-199905000-00007

Intraoperative Fluid Administration in ENT Surgery: Impact on Acid-Base Balance and Renal Function (Experience from a Developing Country)

- VIII. Prough DS, Bidani A: Hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis is a predictable consequence of intraoperative infusion of 0.9% saline. *Anesthesiology*. 1999, 90:1247-1249. 10.1097/00000542-199905000-00003
- IX. M Rehm I, V Orth, S Scheingraber, U Kreimeier, H Brechtelsbauer, U Finsterer : Acid-base changes caused by 5% albumin versus 6% hydroxyethyl starch solution in patients undergoing acute normovolemic hemodilution: a randomized prospective study. *Anesthesiology*. 2000, 93:1174-1183. 10.1097/00000542-200011000-00007
- X. Waters JH, Bernstein CA: Dilutional acidosis following hetastarch or albumin in healthy volunteers .*Anesthesiology*. 2000, 93:1184-1187. 10.1097/00000542-200011000-00008
- XI. Gan TJ, Bennet-Guerrero, Phillips-Butte B, Wakeling H, Moskowitz: Hextend[registered sign], a Physiologically Balanced Plasma Expander for Large Volume Use in Major Surgery: A Randomized Phase III Clinical Trial. *Anesth Analg*. 1999, 88:992-998. 10.1097/00000539-199905000-00005
- XII. Wilcox CS: Regulation of renal blood flow by plasma chloride . *J Clin Invest*. 1983, 71:726-735.10.1172/jci110820
- XIII. Eberhard LW, Morabito DJ, Matthay MA, Mackersie RC, Campbell AR: Initial severity of metabolic acidosis predicts the development of acute lung injury in severely traumatized patients. *Crit Care Med*. 2000, 28:125-131. 10.1097/00003246-200001000-00021
- XIV. Hayhoe M, Bellomo R, Liu G, McNicol L, Buxton B: The aetiology and pathogenesis of cardiopulmonary bypass-associated metabolic acidosis using polygeline pump prime. *Intensive Care Med*. 1999, 25:680-685.10.1007/s001340050930
- XV. Skellett S, Mayer A, Durward A, Tibby SM, Murdoch IA: Chasing the base deficit: hyperchloraemic acidosis following 0.9% saline fluid resuscitation. *Arch Dis Child*. 2000, 83:514-516. 10.1136/adc.83.6.514
- XVI. ANDEM, Société de Réanimation de Langue Française, Société Française d'Anesthésie et de Réanimation: Recommandations pour la pratique clinique: remplissage vasculaire au cours des hypovolémies relatives ou absolues. *Réanim Urgences*. 1997, 6:331-427.14